
The European “Severe Accident Phenomenology” (SAP) short course

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Abstract

The European “Severe Accident Phenomenology” (SAP) short course was launched in 2006 under the 6th EURATOM Framework programme in the frame of the European Severe Accident Research Network of Excellence (SARNET). It established the basis for keeping and transmitting the main knowledge about severe accidents (SA) gained after the Chernobyl accident. Since then, a total of ten SAP short courses have been held between 2006 and 2023. The last course was held in Madrid from 19 to 23 June 2023, at ETSII-UPM, in the framework of the [SEAKNOT project](#)^a. It has been co-organized by UPM (ES), CEA-IRESNE (FR), CIEMAT (ES), University of Pisa (IT) and Jožef Stefan Institute (SI).

The program, developed along 30 hours by 13 expert lecturers, covered the following relevant topics: SA in nuclear power plant (NPP) safety; historical SA: TMI-2, Chernobyl and Fukushima-Daiichi; in-vessel core degradation phenomena: early and late phases; early containment failure: direct containment heating (DCH), hydrogen and CO risk; fuel coolant interaction (FCI) and steam explosions; ex-vessel phase, corium spread; molten core concrete interaction (MCCI), coolability; source term: fission product transport in RCS and containment; source term chemistry; SA computer codes & uncertainty quantification; safety assessment (PSA); SA management guides; radiological impact of SA; decommissioning after SA; new design features for SA mitigation in Gen-III NPPs; SA considerations in Small Modular Reactors (SMR); post-Fukushima safety improvements in Spanish NPP.

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The course was attended by 27 professionals and 33 post-graduate students of 20 nationalities, coming from organizations spanning 14 countries across Europe, America and Asia. They provided a very positive evaluation of the SAP-2023 short course, considering it very useful for their performance in their current positions or to progress in their professional careers. A large majority of responders would recommend it.

The next [SAP-2025 short course](#) is already being scheduled to take place from 23 to 27 June 2025 at FZJ Jülich (Germany), followed by the first edition of the Severe Accident Summer Camp (SASCAMP 2025) from June 30 to July 4, 2025, always in the framework of the SEAKNOT project.

KEY WORDS: SEVERE ACCIDENT PHENOMENOLOGY, SEVERE ACCIDENT RESEARCH, COURSE.

1. INTRODUCTION AND HISTORY

Dissemination of European nuclear safety knowledge is a key-pillar for nuclear education and training. International interest on Severe Accident Phenomenology (SAP) research started soon after TMI-2 accident, with different experimental programmes initiated in the 1980's. The main goal of SAP research was preventing and managing the consequences of a severe accident (SA), which can contribute to greatly reducing the overall risk of nuclear power plants. Since then, SAP has been an important topic on nuclear safety, and one of the main research lines in the successive EURATOM Framework Programmes. Not less important was disseminating the knowledge gained on SAP, and part of it was the organization of thematic conferences and courses. Thus, the first Eurocourses on the subject were organized by UPM in 1997¹ and CEA in 2003².

Taking over from those previous courses, before the Fukushima-Daiichi accident, the European “Severe Accident Phenomenology” short course project had the ambition to train scientists and engineers recently involved in the SA field and coming from all over the world. SAP short courses were also aiming to preserve the high level of European skill in severe accident in order to be useful for research centres and universities, regulatory bodies and nuclear industry. Nine SAP short courses have been held between 2006 and 2021, initially under the umbrella of the European Severe Accident Research Network of Excellence (SARNET), integrated after mid-2013 in NUGENIA and then SNETP/NUGENIA in the EURATOM Framework programs [1].

The first SAP short course was launched in January 2006 under the 6th EURATOM Framework as part of the spreading activities of the SARNET network. It established the basis for keeping and transmitting the main knowledge gained after Chernobyl accident within several national and European SA programs. Much of the understanding and knowledge about the complexity of SAP was also gathered in a textbook (“*Nuclear Safety in Light Water Reactors: Severe Accident Phenomenology*”) edited by Prof. Raj Sehgal and published in 2012 [2] as a product of SARNET, which describes the results from these European research programs, but also the results of SA research conducted in the United States, Japan, Korea, Russia, and other countries.

The European SAP short courses have been since the beginning focused mainly on SAP issues (corium, hydrogen and source term), modelling and codes for Generation 2 and Generation 3 light water reactors, that can be identified in an ideogram elaborated by Prof. Agustín Alonso in 1989 (**Figure 1**) [3]. After the Fukushima-Daiichi accident, the SAP short course evolved, and new lectures were added, focused on the

¹ EURO COURSE-97 “Analysis of Severe Accidents in LWRs” (Polytechnic University of Madrid, 13-17 Oct. 1997).

² EURO COURSE-2003 “Corium: Severe Accident R&D and Nuclear Power Plant Safety” (CEA Cadarache, 27-31 Jan. 2003).

specificity of that accident and its management. More recently, three courses linked to NUGENIA TA2 were held in Ljubljana (2017), Cadarache (2019) and Bologna (2021, online). After the COVID-19 pandemic, the first in-person course, co-organized by UPM (ES), CEA-IRESNE (FR), CIEMAT (ES), University of Pisa (IT) and Jožef Stefan Institute (SI), has been held in Madrid from 19 to 23 June 2023, at ETSII-UPM, in the framework of the [SEAKNOT project](#)^a. [4].

This SAP-2023 short course was dedicated to the knowledge in the SA area gained in the last two decades. In the frame of SEAKNOT project, new or modified lectures have been proposed for SAP-2023 and SAP-2025 regarding last advances in SA knowledge. For Fukushima-Daiichi lectures, the last insights and SA progression understanding is now included. Status of SA codes and their uncertainties have been developed in two lectures. A lecture on Fukushima-Daiichi decommissioning stressed the link between SA progression knowledge and damaged reactors.

Figure 1. Ideogram of phenomena associated with severe accidents in LWR elaborated by Prof. Agustín Alonso in 1989 [2].

2. OBJECTIVES AND ORGANIZATION

As indicated above, the main objective of SAP short courses is the preservation of SA knowledge and its transmission to scientists and engineers dealing with reactor safety in either universities, R&D organizations, safety institutes, utilities or nuclear industry, fostering further development of expertise in the SA field.

Since 90's, national and EU research and development programs have been devoted to the study and modelling of SA key-phenomena. This research area is characterized by scientific and technical challenges due to multiphase flows at high temperatures, complex fluids, and the large span of time scales to be considered. Another topic concerns the life extension of existing reactors (Generation 2) which is envisaged by the utilities and lead the Safety Authorities to ask for a re-evaluation of the safety studies, including SA. At last, the requirement for new reactors (Generation 3) include coping with SA aiming to passively or actively mitigating them.

Looking to facilitate access to all European countries, each SAP short course session has been held in a different country (a European course “in tour”). The lecturers are chosen among the best European experts, scientists and engineers, in the field of SAP R&D, TSO and the nuclear industry.

The last two SAP-courses are organized in the frame of [SEAKNOT project](#)^a: *Severe Accident Research and Knowledge Management for Light-Water Reactors*, a 48-month project funded by the European Union (Horizon Europe), coordinated by CIEMAT (Spain), that brings together 17 partners from 10 European countries. The [SAP-2023 short course](#) has been the first course in presence after the COVID period. It has been held at the Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (ETSII-UPM), in Madrid, Spain from 19 to 23 June, 2023 (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Image of the SAP 2023 short course held at ETSII-UPM (Spain).

Always in the framework of SEAKNOT project, the next [SAP-2025 short course](#) is already being scheduled to take place from 23 to 27 June 2025 at FZJ Jülich (Germany), followed by the first edition of the *Severe Accident Summer Camp* (SASCAMP 2025) from June 30 to July 4, 2025, where qualified Instructors will support small groups of participants while “solving” SA related assignments, sharing their knowledge and knowhow in this area (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3. First announcement of the SAP 2025 short course and the Severe Accident Summer Camp (SASCAMP 2025) at FZJ Jülich (Germany).

To meet these objectives, keeping homogeneity in a course “on tour”, the SAP short course is organized by two committees:

- *Steering Educational Committee*: to propose and choose topics of lectures, to coordinate lectures, to assess level of excellence, to propose lectures to lecturers.
- *Organizing Committee and Local Committee*: to organize agenda, to prepare visit of SA nuclear facility, to propose accommodation, to communicate on SAP.

To increase the impact on the new generation that will be trained in SAs, the SAP short course is allowing the participation of many PhD and Master's students. The tuition fee is significantly reduced for students. Also, the European Nuclear Education Network ([ENEN](#)), and SEAKNOT Project, are providing grants to students to allow them participating in SAP short course. Also, they can obtain 3 ECTS that can be accredited by their universities.

3. PROGRAMME AND TOPICS

The topics selected for the SAP-2023 short course at ETSII-UPM covered all the relevant aspects of SAP, including its applications in nuclear safety. They were the following (with indication of the time assigned):

- Severe Accidents (SA) in Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) Safety (1h)
- Historical Severe Accidents: TMI-2 (1h), Chernobyl (1h), Fukushima-Daiichi (2h)
- Early in-vessel core degradation phenomena (2h)
- Late in-vessel core degradation phenomena (1h)
- Early containment failure. Direct Containment Heating (DCH) (1h)
- Hydrogen risk (2h)
- Fuel coolant interaction (FCI) and steam explosions (2h)
- Ex-vessel phenomena. Corium spread; molten core concrete interaction (MCCI); coolability (2h)
- Source term: FP Transport in RCS and Containment. Source term chemistry (2h)
- Severe Accident computer codes (1h)
- Uncertainty Quantification in Severe Accident Analysis (1h)
- Severe accident management guides (SAMG) (1h)
- Safety assessment (PSA) (1h)
- Post-Fukushima safety improvements in Spanish NPP. Impact on SA phenomenology (1h)
- Long-term accident management (1h)
- Radiological impact of SA (1h)
- Decommissioning after SA (1h)
- New Design Features for Severe Accident Mitigation in Gen-III NPPs (2h)
- Severe accidents in Advanced and SMRs: Issues, challenges, and opportunities (1h)
- Status of SA research (1h)

A visit to the National Nuclear Fusion Laboratory of CIEMAT was also included during the week.

4. PARTICIPATION

As shown in Table I, the attendees had the following distribution between participants, teachers and staff:

- 27 Professional attendees
- 33 post-graduate students attended, of which 25 obtained tuition fee exemption.
- 13 Lecturers + 2 UPM staff

In total, there were participants of 20 nationalities, coming from organizations of 14 countries.

Table I. Distribution of SAP-2023 short course attendees by countries.

Country	Professionals	Students	Lecturers
Belgium	1		1
Canada	2		
Czech Republic	3	2	
Finland	2	1	
France	4	1	4
Germany	4	8	2
Iran		2	
Italy	1	3	2
Mexico	1		
The Netherlands	1		
Slovenia			1
South Korea	4		
Spain	4 (+ 2 UPM staff)	15	3
Sweden		1	

Figure 4. SAP-2023 attendees at ETSII-UPM.

5. ASSESSMENT AND CONCLUSIONS

The course assessment by attendees was based on a questionnaire with 30 questions covering the organizational aspects, the lecturers, the content of the course and the overall usefulness of it. A total of 44 replies were collected, showing a very high level of satisfaction overall (a rating of 5/5 on 22 questions and a rating of 4/5 on the other 8 questions).

Participants were indeed very interactive, with plenty of questions and dialogue with the expert lecturers during the sessions, and a lot of comments and suggestions for improvement in their replies to the questionnaire. On the organizational aspects, there were 49 comments, many of them of satisfaction, but also many proposals that could be considered for future course editions, together with just a few suggestions of improvement concerning organizational aspects. The evaluation of the lecturers, with 9 comments, showed that, obviously, there is always a room for improvement, but the satisfaction with the great knowledge and quality of lecturers was also clear. Regarding content (12 comments) the overall satisfaction was very high and about usefulness, the SAP-2023 course was very positively evaluated by attendees in general, considering it will be useful for their performance at their current jobs or for their professional career development.

A large majority of responders (average rating of 4.7 over 5) would recommend the SAP short course. This is certainly the best indicator of the success of the SAP-2023 short course. The Steering Educational Committee and the Organizing and Local Committee of the next edition, will try to maintain or increase, if possible, that success for the SAP-2025 short course and the later summer camp SASCAMP 2025 at FZJ in Jülich.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] J.P. Van Dorselaere, F. Bréchnignac, F. De Rosa, L.E. Herranz, I. Kljenak, A. Miassoedov, S. Paci, P. Piluso, Trends in severe accident research in Europe: SARNET network from Euratom to NUGENIA, EPJ Nuclear Sciences & Technologies, Volume 3, 2017.
- [2] B. R. Sehgal (ed.), Nuclear Safety in Light Water Reactors. Severe Accident Phenomenology. Academic Press. 2012. ISBN: 978-0-12-388446-6.
- [3] A. Alonso Santos, R. Salve Galiana, L. Rebollo Medrano. El proyecto PHEBUS-CSD en el marco de la investigación sobre accidentes severos. Nuclear España, 94, Enero 1991. <https://www.revistanuclear.es/wp-content/uploads/hemeroteca/094/NE94-03.pdf>
- [4] L.E. Herranz, S. Gupta, P. Piluso, S. Paci, SEAKNOT: Looking Ahead of Severe Accident Research, ERMSAR 2024 Conference, Stockholm (SE), May 13-16, 2024